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ГНІЙНО-ЗАПАЛЬНІ УСКЛАДНЕННЯ ПРИ ХРОНІЧНОМУ АПІКАЛЬНОМУ ПЕРІОДОНТИТІ У ПРИЗОВНИКІВ.

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PURULENT COMPLICATIONS DEVELOPMENT IN PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC APICAL PERIODONTITIS IN CONSCRIPTS

Анотація.

У роботі наведено теоретичне обґрунтування та науково-практичне рішення актуального завдання сучасної стоматології, пов'язаного з удосконаленням методики диференційної діагностики характеру перебігу хронічного апікального періодонтиту, зокрема його деструктивних форм (гранулюючої, гранульоматозної) у призовників. За результатами проведеного дослідження набула подальшого опрацювання і уточнення методика диференційної діагностики характеру перебігу хронічного апікального періодонтиту, його деструктивних форм (гранулюючої, гранульоматозної). Здійснено розробку технології прогнозування активності запальних деструктивних змін, що відбуваються при агресивних формах хронічного апікального періодонтиту, з використанням запропонованого програмного забезпечення. Створено алгоритм диференційної діагностики деструктивних форм хронічного апікального періодонтиту, що передбачає проведення малоінвазивних заходів, як то аналіз біохімічних параметрів ротової рідини пацієнта та розрахунок відповідної ймовірності виникнення тяжких гнійно-запальних ускладнень щелепно-лицевої ділянки, що надасть змогу обрати оптимальну тактику відповідно до ураженого зуба. Вперше досліджено та вивчено кореляційний взаємозв'язок між показниками ротової рідини та периапікальної грануляційної тканини при формах апікального хронічного періодонтиту (фіброзного, гранулюючого, гранульоматозного) з метою прогнозування ризику виникнення ускладнень хронічного периапікального запального процесу, що надасть змогу лікарю-стоматологу обрати оптимальну тактику ведення пацієнта.

Abstract

The paper presents a theoretical justification and scientific and practical solution of the actual problem of modern dentistry related to the improvement of the method of differential diagnosis of the nature of the course of chronic apical periodontitis, in particular its destructive forms (granulating, granulomatous) in conscripts. Based on the results of the study, the method of differential diagnosis of the nature of the course of chronic apical periodontitis, its destructive forms (granulating, granulomatous) was further developed and clarified. A technology for predicting the activity of inflammatory destructive changes that occur in aggressive forms of chronic apical periodontitis is developed using the proposed software. An algorithm for differential diagnosis of destructive forms of chronic apical periodontitis has been developed, which involves minimally invasive measures, such as analyzing the biochemical parameters of the patient's oral fluid and calculating the corresponding probability of severe purulent-inflammatory complications of the maxillofacial region, which will allow choosing the optimal tactics in accordance with the affected tooth. For the first time, the correlation between the parameters of oral fluid and periapical granulation tissue in forms of apical chronic periodontitis (fibrous, granulating, granulomatous) was studied and studied in order to predict the risk of complications of chronic periapical inflammatory process, which will allow the dentist to choose the optimal patient management tactics.

Ключові слова: призовники збройних сил України, хронічний апікальний періодонтит, запальний процес, ускладнення.

Keywords: *conscripts of the Armed Forces of Ukraine, chronic apical periodontitis, inflammatory process, complications.*

Apical periodontitis is a chronic inflammatory disorder of periradicular tissues caused by aetiological agents of endodontic origin. Persistent apical periodontitis occurs when root canal treatment of apical periodontitis has not adequately eliminated intraradicular infection. Problems that lead to persistent apical periodontitis include: inadequate aseptic control, poor access cavity design, missed canals, inadequate instrumentation, debridement and leaking temporary or permanent restorations. [1-7].

According to the results of the study, the technique of differential diagnosis of the character of the course of chronic apical periodontitis, in particular its destructive forms (granulating, granulomatous), was improved. The technology of predicting the activity of inflammatory destructive changes that occur in aggressive forms of chronic apical periodontitis using the created software is developed. An algorithm for differential diagnosis of destructive forms of chronic apical periodontitis, which involves the implementation of minimally invasive methods, such as analysis of biochemical parameters of oral fluid of the patient and calculation of the approximate incidence probability of severe purulent-inflammatory complications of the maxillofacial area in patients. For the first time, the correlation between oral fluid and periapical granulation tissue in the forms of apical chronic periodontitis (fibrous, granulating, granulomatous) was investigated and studied in order to predict the risk of complications of chronic periapical inflammation for the further selection of treatment procedures.

Materials and methods. The results of the dissertation are based on the survey data of 140 patients aged 18 to 22 years, who gave written consent to conduct a comprehensive clinical, radiological, histological and biochemical study. In 120 of them, some form of chronic apical periodontitis was diagnosed, and 20 patients formed a control group (somatically and dental healthy patients).

Criteria for inclusion of patients in study groups:

1. Age of patients 18-22 years.
2. Verified diagnosis of chronic apical inflammatory process, complicated or uncomplicated disease course (except control group).
3. Absence of corresponding acute or chronic infectious somatic disorders, oncological diseases.
4. Absence of oral mucosa inflammation and parodontal diseases.
5. Informative written consent of the patient to conduct a comprehensive study.

The following study groups were selected among the total number of patients (140):

1. A control group comprising 20 people (14.3 %) – somatically and dental healthy patients.
2. The group of patients with diagnosed chronic apical periodontitis was 100 (71.4 %). Among them, the following clinical and morphological forms of chronic apical periodontitis were determined: chronic fibrous apical periodontitis was diagnosed in 21 pa-

tients (15 %), destructive forms of chronic apical periodontitis (granulating and granulomatous) were detected in 30 (21.4 %) and 49 patients (35 %) respectively.

3. Patients with complicated course of chronic apical periodontitis (20 patients, 14.3 %), depending on the severity of the acute inflammatory process, were further divided into the following subgroups: patients with middle-grade purulent-inflammatory complications (acute purulent odontogenic periostitis, periapical abscess) – 12 patients (8.6 %); patients with severe purulent-inflammatory complications of chronic apical periodontitis (acute odontogenic osteomyelitis, odontogenic phlegmon) – 8 patients (5.7 %).

The required set of diagnostic measures was performed for the patients of each study group. The list of performed diagnostic methods among the study groups was not homogeneous, which, in fact, was due to the need and the ability to perform each technique. Clinical examination was performed in all 140 patients (control group patients, patients with chronic apical periodontitis, and patients with purulent-inflammatory complications of chronic apical periodontitis). A radiographic study involving targeted contact visiography, orthopantomography (panoramic scan), and cone-beam computed tomography were performed in patients with clinical forms of chronic apical periodontitis (fibrous, granulating, granulomatous) and patients with severe purulent-inflammatory complications of chronic apical periodontitis (120 patients). A comprehensive biochemical study of oral fluid, blood serum, and pathologically modified periapical tissue was performed. Indicators such as the degree of oral cavity dysbiosis, malondialdehyde content, antioxidant-prooxidant index, enzyme activity (lysozyme, urease, elastase, and acidic phosphatase) were determined in oral fluid and blood serum. The research was conducted on patients of all study groups (140 patients). Biochemical analysis of pathologically affected periapical tissue was performed in patients with destructive forms of chronic apical inflammation (granulating, granulomatous form of chronic apical periodontitis) and in patients with severe purulent-inflammatory complications of chronic apical periodontitis (99 patients).

Mathematical analysis of the estimated parameters was carried out given the obtained indicators on the basis of the performed researches (140 patients).

Clinical examination of patients revealed the features of the clinical course of the disease; in particular, depending on the clinical presentation and pathoanatomical structure, therefore chronic apical periodontitis could be conditionally divided into such forms as stable and active. Chronic apical fibrous periodontitis is considered a stabilized form, active (destructive) forms are – granulating and granulomatous chronic apical periodontitis. Thus, it is advisable to determine the following nosological forms of chronic apical periodontitis: chronic apical fibrous periodontitis, chronic destructive (granulating, granulomatous) apical periodontitis and chronic apical periodontitis in the exacerbated state.

The proposed classification is consistent with the ICD-10: International Statistical Classification of Diseases and Related Health Problems (10th Revision).

Results and their condemnation. Given the clinical parameters identified in the study groups, the following features of the clinical course of chronic apical periodontitis can be observed. Thus, the incidence of chronic apical periodontitis in most cases was preceded by the presence of a carious cavity in the causal tooth, which was more often associated with its cavity, except for 5 patients who were diagnosed with fibrous form of chronic apical periodontitis, and 6 patients with granulomatous chronic apical periodontitis. Therefore, it is possible to suspect the non-odontogenic nature of the occurrence of chronic apical periodontitis, in particular traumatic. Among patients in all comparison groups, there was no pain while probing the walls or bottom of the carious cavity, as well as the effects of chemical and term stimuli. Most patients reveal spontaneous pain (18, 25, 42 patients according to the order of the comparison groups). Patients of all comparison groups note the frequency of pain. The nature and duration of pain vary. The presence of changes in oral mucosa in the projection of the pathological cell (edema, hyperemia) was detected only in patients with a granulating form of chronic apical periodontitis. No similar changes were observed in patients with fibrous and granulomatous forms of chronic apical periodontitis. Smoothness of the transitional fold of the alveolar process was absent in patients with fibrous chronic apical periodontitis, in contrast to the group of patients with granulomatous form of chronic apical periodontitis, where this symptom was present in 6 patients, and patients with granulating form of chronic apical periodontitis, where the smoothness was present among all patients within the group. Most patients in the comparison groups indicate the presence of pain in apical percussion. The mobility of the affected tooth is present in the majority of patients with the granulating form of chronic apical periodontitis, in patients of the remaining groups this symptom is absent. Most patients in all comparison groups had prior endodontic treatment of the affected teeth. The initiation of chronic apical inflammatory process in this case usually indicates the presence of certain incorrect manipulations during endodontic treatment. The presence of purulent exudation from the fistula or root canal system was noted in the majority of patients with a granulating form of chronic apical periodontitis (21 patients). Changes in tooth color were observed in patients in all comparison groups (14, 18, 39 patients according to the order of study groups). Increase of regional lymph nodes is present in 20 patients with granulomatous form of chronic apical periodontitis, in other patients it is absent. Symptoms of general intoxication of the organism were observed in 20 patients with granulomatous form of chronic apical periodontitis, in all 39 patients with granulating form of chronic apical periodontitis, in patients with fibrous form of chronic apical periodontitis were absent.

The following radiological parameters were observed among the study groups: the presence of the area of bone sclerosis in the pathological area, the prevalence of the pathological area on the surrounding teeth,

the volume of the pathological area (the size of the zone of destruction of bone tissue), the destruction of the root of the tooth, the presence and quality of root canal obturation to the radiographic apex or partial obturation, the nature of the endodontic material for root canal obturation and the density of obturation, available number of additional root canals and their branches), the nature of the relation of the pathological area to the maxillary sinus and the vascular-nerve bundle (presence of penetration).

According to the results, in chronic apical fibrous periodontitis certain parameters are visualized in sufficient detail. The following inaccuracies were noted: no visualization of the bone sclerosis area on the panoramic scan, low informativeness of the image regarding the quality of the previous endodontic treatment on the panoramic scan, and contact target visigraphy (possibility of the existence of an auxiliary root canal or its branch). Instead, a cone-beam computer image provides a detailed radiological view of the nature of the pathological region, in particular, the ability to obtain images in three dimensions (frontal, sagittal, transverse) allows to fully visualize the nature of the relationship of the pathological region to maxillary sinus or vascular-nerve bundle, spread of pathologic focus of inflammation to the adjacent anatomical structures, the volume of the pathological region (the zone of bone tissue destruction), as well as features of root canal structure (the presence of additional root canal or branches) for planning endodontic re-treatment.

Concerning biochemical analysis of oral fluid of patients in the study groups we obtained the following results. Oral fluid in patients with asymptomatic chronic apical periodontitis witnessed significant reduction by 60.5 % in the activity of one of the main enzymes of the antioxidant system of oral cavity protection, i.e. catalase ($p < 0.001$). As a result of incompetence of the antioxidant system in oral cavity of these patients, a high intensity of lipid peroxidation was observed, as evidenced by an increase in malonic dialdehyde content by 2.54 times ($p < 0.05$) in oral fluid of this group compared to normative values. Detected changes led to a decrease of the API (antioxidant-prooxidant index) characterizing the state of POL-AOS in oral fluid of a group of patients with uncomplicated course of chronic apical periodontitis from 2.65 to 0.41. It confirms a shift of the equilibrium of the specified system in the direction of intensification of the peroxide oxidation of lipids.

In oral fluid of patients with purulent-inflammatory complications of chronic apical periodontitis, the activity of catalase was reduced to a much greater extent ($p < 0.001$ and $p_1 < 0.01$), however, the content of malonic dialdehyde remained at the level of the group of patients with uncomplicated course of chronic apical periodontitis ($p_1 > 0.1$). The antioxidant-prooxidant index decreased to 0.23, indicating that the level of antioxidant protection in oral cavity of patients with severe inflammatory complications of chronic apical periodontitis is extremely low.

In oral fluid of patients with uncomplicated chronic apical periodontitis, lysozyme activity was reduced, although not significantly, by 1.49 times

($p > 0.05$) with a simultaneous increase in urease activity by 2.53 times ($p < 0.05$). The results obtained indicate a decrease in antibacterial protection in oral cavity of patients with uncomplicated course of chronic apical periodontitis, resulting in significantly increased pathogenic bacterial contamination of oral cavity. More clearly this phenomenon demonstrates an index dysbiosis condition, which increases in oral fluid of patients with uncomplicated course of chronic apical periodontitis by 3.73 times.

In patients in the study group with severe purulent-inflammatory complications of chronic apical periodontitis, lysozyme activity was significantly reduced by 3.08 times ($p < 0.001$ and $p_1 < 0.01$) with correspondence of a significant increase in urease activity ($p < 0.001$ and $p_1 < 0.02$), which almost 5 times exceeds the normal level. The result of such significant disorders in the system of microbiocenosis of oral cavity of patients with severe purulent complications of chronic apical periodontitis is an increase in the degree of dysbiosis by 15.4 times.

In oral fluid of patients with uncomplicated course of chronic apical periodontitis there is a marked tendency to increase of acidic phosphatase activity ($p < 0.05$), which indicates a violation of the integrity of the cell membranes of oral tissues, which in turn is a characteristic of the inflammatory process. Incidentally, in oral fluid of patients with uncomplicated chronic apical periodontitis the content of such a marker of inflammation as elastase activity ($p < 0.02$) grew more than twice. In patients with severe purulent inflammatory complications, inflammatory markers are significantly increased, even compared with the corresponding rates of patients with uncomplicated periapical inflammation ($p < 0.001$ and $p_1 < 0.001$ for both elastase and acidic phosphatase).

Thus, the results obtained indicate that patients with severe purulent complications of chronic apical periodontitis have more severe disorders of oral cavity homeostasis: in the system of POL-AOS (decrease in catalase activity, increase in the level of antibacterial activity (decrease in antibacterial activity) lysozyme content), increased contamination of conditionally pathogenic microflora (increased urease activity) and intensification of inflammatory processes in oral cavity.

Analyzing the data of biochemical study of pathologically altered periapical tissue, we obtained the following results. The activity of lysozyme in pathologically altered periapical tissue of patients with moderately severe purulent inflammatory complications reduced 2.19 times, and the minimal activity of the specified antimicrobial enzyme is reported in the subgroup of patients with ultra severe purulent inflammatory complications of chronic apical periodontitis (acute odontogenic osteomyelitis, odontogenic phlegmon) – 6.7 times lower against the subgroup of patients with uncomplicated course of chronic apical periodontitis. Urease activity, on the other hand, increased 2.65 times and 7.0 times in patients with moderate and ultra-severe purulent inflammatory complications of chronic apical periodontitis. The content of elastase goes up significantly aligned with the growth of inflammation

aggressiveness. Elastase activity in these subgroups increased by 85.5 % and 244.5 %, respectively, compared to the data of patients with uncomplicated course of chronic apical periodontitis.

Analysis of the pathomorphological structure of pathologically altered periapical tissue allowed us to distinguish fundamental differences among the forms of chronic apical periodontitis. The presence of granulation tissue indicates an inactive chronic course of a productive inflammatory process. The presence of connective tissue (pink stained collagen fibers, hematoxylin-eosin) with minor lymphocytic infiltration, as well as cystic cavities and xanthoma cells in the absence of leukocyte or lymphoid-macrophage infiltration of chronic inflammatory infiltration. These morphological features were determined in biopsies of pathologically affected tissue of patients diagnosed with a granulomatous form of chronic apical periodontitis (granuloma, cystogranuloma).

The tendency to exacerbation of chronic periapical inflammatory process is indicated by the appearance of focal leukocyte and lymphoid-macrophage infiltration and signs of destruction of collagen fibers in the biopsy of the pathologically affected tissue. The described histological structure of biopsy specimens confirms the previously established diagnosis of chronic apical granulation periodontitis in patients of the study group without clinical signs of exacerbation, but with a clear tendency towards it.

The formation of local cell infiltration with a large number of leukocytes in the periodontium is accompanied by the formation of microabscesses. There are swollen collagen fibers around the abscess. In the tissues surrounding the abscess, diffuse lymphoid-macrophage infiltration with a large number of leukocytes was detected. The emergence of abundant diffuse leukocyte and lymphoid-macrophage infiltration (yellow cells with black nuclei, stained by Van-Gizon), as well as the formation of microabscesses surrounded by a fibrous membrane, in the tissue of the biopsy testify the course of active process of intensification. Clinically similar changes in the morphological structure of the periapical tissue correspond to exacerbation of chronic apical periodontitis (acute odontogenic periostitis, osteomyelitis, odontogenic phlegmon).

Conclusions. According to the results of biochemical study of serum, oral fluid and pathologically altered periapical tissue, precise mathematical analysis was carried out with its results illustrated by graphs. According to the results of the biochemical study, the graphs of dependence of the biochemical parameters, which were displayed as a direct (increasing or decreasing) or exponential dependence, were modeled.

We summarized the results of the study shown in the graphs: there is a linear increasing dependence of catalase activity on the activity of lysozyme; exponential growth of dependence of antioxidant-prooxidant index on lysozyme activity; linear decreasing dependence of malonic dialdehyde (MDA) content on lysozyme activity; exponential decreasing dependence of acidic phosphatase activity on lysozyme activity; linear decrease in the dependence of urease activity on the ac-

tivity of lysozyme, and linear increase in the dependence of the concentration of trypsin inhibitor on the concentration of lysozyme.

To simplify the visualization of the indicated correlation dependences, the data analyzed using the graphs was generalized, which allowed to initiate the creation of computer software that models necessary conditions for predicting the course of chronic apical periodontitis in the presence of the results of biochemical analysis of oral fluid and blood serum for the patients by estimating the features of chronic apical inflammatory process and determining the possibility of complications occurrence.

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